

AYURVEDIC APPROACH TO PRATHAMA PATALAGATA TIMIRA (MYOPIA): A CASE STUDY ON CLINICAL EFFICACY

Dr. Sunil Kumar Chahil^{*1}, Dr. Mahima Choudhary², Dr. Prabhakar Vardhan³, Dr. Aanchal Sharma⁴

¹P.G. Scholar, Department of *Shalaky Tantra*, National Institute of Ayurveda Deemed to be University, Jaipur.

²Ph.D. Scholar, Department of *Shalaky Tantra*, National Institute of Ayurveda Deemed to be University, Jaipur.

³Professor, Department of *Shalaky Tantra*, National Institute of Ayurveda Deemed to be University, Jaipur.

⁴U.G. Scholar, National Institute of Ayurveda Deemed to be University, Jaipur.

*Corresponding Author: Dr. Sunil Kumar Chahil

P.G. Scholar, Department of *Shalaky Tantra*, National Institute of Ayurveda Deemed to be University, Jaipur. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20444191>

How to cite this Article: Dr. Sunil Kumar Chahil^{*1}, Dr. Mahima Choudhary², Dr. Prabhakar Vardhan³, Dr. Aanchal Sharma⁴ (2026). Ayurvedic Approach To Prathama Patalagata Timira (Myopia): A Case Study On Clinical Efficacy. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Life Sciences, 12(6), 159–162.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

Article Received on 25/04/2026

Article Revised on 16/05/2026

Article Published on 01/06/2026

ABSTRACT

Myopia is the predominant refractive disorder observed in clinical settings and has emerged as a global public health concern due to its increasing prevalence and lifelong consequences. Previously considered a purely optical issue addressed with glasses or contact lenses, Myopia is now recognized as a multifaceted biological condition characterized by ocular growth dysregulation with environmental factors and genetic predisposition playing a role. Its primary symptom is blurred vision when viewing distant objects. Although corrective lenses can improve vision, Myopia often progresses with age particularly in children. *Prathama Patalagata Timira* in Ayurveda have same clinical features as Myopia. In this case, a twenty-two-year-old male boy presented with complaints of blurred distance vision, watering of eyes and pain in the eyebrow region. He had been using spectacles for three years and his unaided distant visual acuity was 6/12. Based on his symptoms, the condition was diagnosed as *Prathama Patalagata Timira* (Myopia). Management involved *Triphaladi Netra Parisheka*, *Ksheerbala Taila Marsha Nasya*, *Jeevantiyadi Ghritha Tarpana*, *Saptamrita Lauha* with *Mahatriphla Ghritha* and Honey and *Draksharishtha* over a period of four months. Following treatment, his unaided distant visual acuity improved to 6/9, with no observed progression during the follow-up period.

KEYWORDS: Myopia, *Prathama Patalagata Timira*, *Triphaladi Netra Parisheka*, *Jeevantiyadi Ghritha Tarpana*.

INTRODUCTION

Myopia is a widespread refractive error that can reduce visual clarity, limit career choices and increase the likelihood of other eye disorders, making early management important. Myopia, also known as Nearsightedness, is the most frequently occurring refractive error among children and young adults.^[1] It has become an increasing concern, largely due to inadequate awareness and common misconceptions among parents.^[2] According to Guyton's Physiology, the pathophysiology of this condition is that when the ciliary muscle is fully relaxed, light rays from distant objects are brought to a focus in front of the retina rather than directly on it.^[3] This optical mismatch occurs due to excessive elongation of the eyeball or an increase in the refractive power of the cornea and lens. The significant

impact of ocular disorders is explained through the concept of *Drishtigata Rogas*, which includes 76 eye diseases (*Netravadyahi*) described by *Acharya Sushruta*, within this classification, *Acharya Sushruta* specifically details 12 *Drushtigata Rogas*, whereas *Acharya Vagbhata* describes 27 such conditions.

In Ayurveda, the development and severity of *Timira* are closely associated with the involvement of different *Patalas* of the eye. These layered structures are essential in determining the onset and progression of *Timira*. *Timira* denotes darkness, and conditions involving a gradual decline in vision that may eventually lead to blindness are classified under it. According to *Acharya Sushruta*,^[4] *Timira*, *Kacha* and *Linganasha* represent three progressive stages of the same disease, with the

final stage resulting in complete blindness. The prevalence of Myopia is increasing globally due to demographic and lifestyle alterations. Current forecasts suggest that by 2050, 4.8 to 5 billion people will have Myopia, with 1 billion experiencing high Myopia, constituting a significant global health challenge.^[5] Due to its importance as a global public health issue, Myopia was included as a priority condition under Vision 2020, the World Health Organization's worldwide initiative aimed at eliminating avoidable blindness by the year 2020.^[6] Research indicates that progression tends to be faster in children, especially those who have more than one diopter of Myopia at the time of diagnosis compared to those with one diopter or less. *Timira* is further described in stages, where the vitiation of *Doshas* affects the different *Patalas* (layers) of the eye, which are arranged one behind the other. When the first, or outermost, *Patala* is involved, the condition is mild; however, as the inner *Patalas* become affected, it can progress to more severe ocular disorders. Among its progressive stages, *Prathama Patalagata Timira* where the vitiated *Doshas* affect the outermost layer of the eye is correlated with simple Myopia. Its characteristic feature, *Avyakta Darshana* (unclear or blurred vision), closely resembles the distant vision impairment seen in Myopia. Classical Ayurveda texts also describe contributing factors such as prolonged near or far vision work, exposure to dust and smoke, and improper visual practices, which are comparable to modern-day risk factors.

CASE STUDY

Patient History

A 22-year-old male presented with the primary complaint of difficulty in seeing distant objects for the past three years. The onset was gradual. He also reported watering of the eyes during prolonged use of computers and mobile phones and intermittent headache since 1 month. No significant past medical and surgical history was present. Earlier three years ago he underwent an eye examination and was diagnosed with Myopia and he had been using spectacles for the past three years, however, as his refractive power was increasing, he came to the OPD for consultation.

Family History

Patient's father and her older sister use corrective lenses for Myopia. There was no family history of pathological Myopia, Retinal disorders, Diabetes, Hypertension or any cardiac diseases.

Personal History

The patient follows a non-vegetarian diet. He has a good appetite with regular hunger patterns. He reports sound sleep, Bowel movements are regular with normal color and consistency and urination is normal.

Physical Examination

All general physical parameters were within normal limits. According to Ayurveda assessment, the

Ashtavidha Pariksha findings are summarized in below table.

Eye Examination

• <i>Nadi</i> (Pulse)	76/min
• <i>Mootra</i> (Urine)	Normal
• <i>Mala</i> (Stool)	Normal
• <i>Jihwa</i> (Tongue)	Clean (uncoated)
• <i>Shabda</i> (Speech)	Normal
• <i>Sparsha</i> (Touch)	Normal
• <i>Drika</i> (Vision)	Defect in vision
• <i>Akruti</i> (Body build)	Normal

On physical examination, structures such as the eyebrows, eyelashes, eyelids, conjunctiva, sclera, and cornea of both eyes appeared normal. Functional assessment of vision was carried out using a Snellen chart and an Auto refractor.

Visual Acuity	Right Eye	Left Eye
Unaided Far	6/12	6/9 P
Unaided Near	N/6	N/6

Treatment

The patient was instructed to follow three months of treatment regimen as given below and a notable improvement in condition was observed in the patient. *Triphaladi Netra Parisheka* (*Triphala* 3 gm, *Yasthimadhu* 1gm, *Lodhra* 1 gm) and *Ksheerbala Taila Marsha Nasya* (8-8 drops both Nostrils) early in the morning for five days later *Jeevanti Ghrita Tarpana* for seven days. Orally *Saptamrita Lauha* (500mg) with *Mahatriphla Ghrita* (1/2tsf) and Honey (1 tsf) and *Draksharishtha* (30 ml) after food twice a day over a period of thirty days, such complete treatment protocol was followed for four consecutive months. Following treatment, after four months his unaided distant visual acuity was improved to 6/9 (Right) and 6/6P (Left) with no observed progression during the follow-up period.

OBSERVATION

The patient noticed improvement within the first fifteen days of treatment, particularly a soothing effect in the eyes, watering of the eyes was resolved and eye strain also subsided. He also reported feeling more physically active and experienced a sense of lightness in the *Urdhwajatru* portion of body. After four months' vision was reassessed using a Snellen chart and an auto refractor. The findings are presented as given in below table.

Visual Acuity	Right Eye	Left Eye
Unaided Far	6/9	6/6P

DISCUSSION

Myopia is a common refractive error of the eye with a high and increasing prevalence. The prevalence of these errors is growing during these years and gradually it is being recognized as a public health issue.^[7] The rise in

cases is largely attributed to the growing use of digital devices such as mobile phones, televisions, video games, and laptops.^[8] Reduced outdoor activities, poor dietary habits/inadequate nutrition or increased consumption of junk food also contribute to the progression of Myopia. According to Ayurveda, *Prathama Patalagata Timira* is believed to arise from the vitiation of the *Rasa* and *Rakta Dhatus*.^[9] According to *Acharya Nimi*, *Timira* progresses gradually because the involvement of the *Patalas* develops slowly and is painless, which often leads to it being neglected.^[10] *Parisheka* is a type of *Kriyakalpa* that provides a significant local therapeutic effect of the medicines and offers effective relief from the local signs and symptoms of eye disorders. *Nasya Karma* is process where in the oil prepared from drugs is poured through the nostrils and nose is the gate way of head so it is highly effective in curing a number of diseases pertaining to the head. *Nasya* if done properly it cleanses and open the channel of head. There by improving the process of oxygenation *Prana* which has direct influence on the functioning of Brain.^[11] The possible mode of action of *Ksheerabala Taila* can be understood through its *Rasa Panchaka*. All its three ingredients which are *Bala*, *Ksheera* and *Tila Taila* possess *Madhura Rasa* and *Madhura Vipaka*. *Madhura Rasa* is known to pacify both *Vata* and *Pitta Doshas*. *Ksheerabala Taila* is also having role as a *Rasayana* medicine in traditional Ayurveda management. Regular use of this formulation helps in preventing sudden electrical discharges and supports improvement in both the physical and mental health of the patient. It is also known to have a strong calming and relaxing effect on the mind.^[12] *Nasya* with *Ksheerabala Taila* helps in supporting nerve regeneration and strengthening the muscles due to its *Balya* and *Brimhana* properties so helpful in Myopia. Considering *Jeevantyadi Ghrita Tarpana Doshakarma*, the drug is primarily *Vatashamaka*, followed by *Pittashamaka* and *Kaphashamaka* effects based on its *Rasa*, *Guna*, *Veerya*, and *Vipaka*. Overall, the formulation exhibits a *Vata* dominant *Tridosha* pacifying action. Therefore, it helps in breaking the pathological process of *Timira*, which is also a *Vata* predominant *Tridoshaja* condition in its manifestation.

Jeevantyadi Ghrita contains high levels of antioxidants, which help in reducing oxidative stress and preventing damage to the thinned cornea. *Ghrita* is considered one of the best *Rasayana* preparations, while *Jivanti* is regarded as a main *Chakshushya* drug. Most of the ingredients present in *Jeevantyadi Ghrita* possess *Tridosha-shamaka* properties. Moreover, the *Ghrita* preparation used in *Akshi Tarpana* is in the form of a suspension containing fine drug particles, which remain in contact with the eye for a longer duration compared to solutions that are quickly washed away. This increased contact time enhances tissue absorption and bioavailability, thereby helping achieve effective therapeutic concentrations through *Akshi Tarpana*. From the perspective of modern medical science, there is currently no fully satisfactory medical treatment

available for Myopia. In Ayurveda texts, *Acharya Govind Das Sen* in *Bhaishajya Ratnavali* has recommended *Saptamrita Lauha* for the management of *Timira*. Nutritional factors also play an important role in the management of *Timira*. Ayurveda describes the *Chakshushya* (vision-promoting) properties of certain drugs such as *Triphala*, *Yashtimadhu* and *Lauha Bhasma*. A combination of these drugs in the form of an oral supplement may therefore be beneficial in managing Myopia. *Mahatriphaladi Ghrita*, which is indicated in *Timira*, contains ingredients such as *Triphala*, *Shatavari*, *Guduchi*, *Ajaksheera*, *Draksha*, *Yashtimadhu*, *Ksheera Kakoli*, *Madhuyashti*, *Nidigdika*, *Neelotpala*, *Pippali*, and *Goghrita*. Most of these drugs possess *Madhura Rasa*, *Sheeta Veerya* and *Madhura Vipaka* along with *Chakshushya* properties and in addition, many of them have antioxidant activity, which helps in neutralizing free radicals and reducing oxidative damage to ocular tissues. *Drakshasava* given is a fermented preparation that supports ocular health mainly due to its high nutritional value and its role in enhancing *Rasa Dhatu* (tissue nourishment) so helpful in Myopia.

CONCLUSION

Therefore, these above interventions *Triphaladi Netra Parisheka*, *Ksheerbala Taila Marsha Nasya*, *Jeevantyadi Ghrita Tarpana*, *Saptamrita Lauha* with *Mahatriphala Ghrita* and Honey and *Draksharishtha* may be useful in Myopic patients for preventing, delaying or managing the condition and also subsiding various additional symptoms such as strain, headache in Myopes.

REFERENCES

1. Baird PN, Saw SM, Lanca C, Guggenheim JA, Smith Iii EL, Zhou X, Matsui KO, Wu PC, Sankaridurg P, Chia A, Rosman M, Lamoureux EL, Man R, He M. Myopia. Nat Rev Dis Primers, 2020 Dec 17; 6(1): 99.
2. Kaiti R, Pradhan A, Dahal HN, Shrestha P. Pattern and Prevalence of Refractive Error and Secondary Visual Impairment in Patients Attending a Tertiary Hospital in Dhulikhel, Nepal. Kathmandu Univ Med J (KUMJ), 2018 Apr-Jun; 16(62): 114-119.
3. Guyton A, Hall J, Text book on Medical physiology, Pennsylvania, Elsevier Inc. ed-11, pg 619.
4. Acharya Sushrutha, Sharma A, Sushrutha Samhitha, Varanasi, Chaukambha surabharathi prakashan, 2013; p.53.
5. Holden BA, Fricke TR, Wilson DA, Jong M, Naidoo KS, Sankaridurg P, Wong TY, Naduvilath TJ, Resnikoff S. Global Prevalence of Myopia and High Myopia and Temporal Trends from 2000 through 2050. Ophthalmology, 2016 May; 123(5): 1036-42.
6. McCarty CA, Taylor HR. Myopia and vision 2020. Am J Ophthalmol, 2000; 129: 525-7.
7. Hashemi H, Fotouhi A, Yekta A, Pakzad R, Ostadimoghaddam H, Khabazkhoob M. Global and regional estimates of prevalence of refractive errors: Systematic review and meta-analysis. J Curr Ophthalmol, 2018; 30: 3-22.

8. Enthoven CA, Tideman JW, Polling JR, Yang-Huang J, Raat H, Klaver CC. The impact of computer use on myopia development in childhood: The Generation R study. *Prev Med*, 2020; 132: 105988.
9. Shankar Udaya, Text book of Shalaky Tantra, Varanasi: Chaukambha Vishva bharathi, 2018; p 561.
10. Shankar Udaya, Text book of Shalaky Tantra, Varanasi: Chaukambha Vishva bharathi, 2018; p 560.
11. Agnivesa, Caraka Samhita, Vidyotini Hindi Commentary by Pt. Kasinath Sastri and Dr. Gorakha Natha Chaturvedi, Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, Varanasi, Reprint, 2009; 331.
12. Nimmy et. al. A Comparative Study on Anticonvulsant Effect of Ksheerabala Taila-Ayurveda Formulation Made with Two Source Plants of Bala (*Sida Cordifolia* Linn. And *Sida Retusa* Linn.). *IAMJ*, 2017; 1(5): 549-56.